

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF DEVELOPING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. This article provides information on modern approaches in the field of preschool education, discussion of issues of improving the quality of education and ensuring its effectiveness, scientific and practical work to identify existing problems in the field and eliminate them, as well as information on the further development of the education system through innovative methods of developing preschool children.

Keywords: modern approach, innovation, preschool age, development centers, methodology, method, child, preschool education, upbringing, development areas.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о современных подходах в сфере дошкольного образования, обсуждение вопросов повышения качества образования и обеспечения его эффективности, научно-практическая работа по выявлению существующих проблем в сфере и их устранению, а также информация о дальнейшем развитии системы образования за счет инновационных методов развития детей дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: современный подход, инновация, дошкольный возраст, центры развития, методика, метод, ребенок, дошкольное образование, воспитание, направления развития.

The reforms implemented in our country in the field of education, including the development of the preschool education system, its goals, objectives, main ideas of educational and educational activities, as well as the systematic and consistent development of the child's basic competencies in the transition to a wide stage of education, are paying great attention. Important tasks have been set, such as "radically improving all conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of the child, significantly increasing the coverage of children with preschool education and ensuring their accessibility, and improving the qualification level of teachers and specialists." The concept "Development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was developed in our republic by Decree No. PQ-4312 dated May 8, 2019. The concept defines the goals, objectives, priority areas, medium- and long-term stages of the development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and serves as the basis for the development of programs and comprehensive measures aimed at the development of the preschool education sector [1].

Play is the child's natural environment, and the child's inclinations, emotions, understanding, and creative abilities are adapted to the game. The game can be of various types - games that are carried out completely independently, on the initiative of the child or a group of children, or with minimal or complete participation of the teacher, as well as games that are organized by the teacher or with the help of his instructions. The game is considered for the child both a means of entertainment and a way of learning, as well as a way of implementing the creative ideas of the child in his own imagination. The main advantage of game activity over other types of activity is that it is active and free. In preschool children, abilities and the concept of "personality" are formed not in education or conversations, but precisely through play. In addition to providing a good mood for children, play serves to develop their emotional

development, figurative thinking, imagination, and speech. Because children with a well-developed imagination are children with high intelligence, and this, in turn, allows them to learn well and quickly find their way in unfamiliar situations [2].

In 2018, the separation of the field of preschool education as a separate ministry was the prelude to the greatest attention directed to preschool education, which is considered the initial link of continuous education. After that, the first step is the adoption of the state curriculum, the improvement of the program, the adoption of the concept is one of the opportunities created for preschool children to receive quality education and training. If we take into account that a child can receive 70% of knowledge about the world by the age of 5, this period corresponds to the child's preschool age [3].

In our republic, normative foundations are being created for the effective formation of innovative ideas and imagination of preschool children, optimization of the content and form of education, and organization of educational processes. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Preschool Education and Education” sets out such priority tasks as “the introduction of modern innovative and information and communication technologies in order to create alternative forms of education and upbringing of children and their comprehensive development”. One of the current directions in the process of preschool education is to improve the content and technology of high-quality preparation of children for primary school education using a pedagogical innovation cluster. In implementing the above processes, we must pay special attention to the correct organization of activities carried out in preschool education and the technologies used in the implementation of these activities.

Activity is a specific form of social and historical existence of people, their purposeful transformation of natural and social reality. Activity includes a goal, means, result and process. Pedagogical activity is a type of social activity aimed at transferring the culture and experience accumulated by mankind from the older generation to the younger generation, creating conditions for their personal development and preparing them to fulfill certain social roles in society. In a word, the holistic pedagogical process is a process that, in its content, combines “educational education” and “educational education”.(ADisterweg).

The word technology is derived from the Greek word and means “technos” - art, skill, “logos” - teaching. In the history of the formation and development of the concept of pedagogical technology, there were different views: it was interpreted as a doctrine of technical means, and as a planned, consistent and systematic organization of the educational process. Currently, there are several definitions of pedagogical technologies.

Pedagogical technology is the application of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of education and upbringing, studies the problems of increasing the effectiveness of the educational and upbringing process based on a technological approach. There are various forms and methods of developing the skills of educators, which can be implemented step by step.

An example of the most widely used pedagogical technologies in preschool educational organizations is game technology. Because the use of games in educating children aged 3-7 creates wider opportunities. Providing new knowledge to the child in the process of classes organized within each age group helps to increase its effectiveness [3]. The use of game technologies in further improving pedagogical processes can also contribute to further improving quality. Because in the process of play, positive socialization and mental (psychological) processes are formed in the child: attention, memory, imagination, speech. The game also gives

children joy, evokes various emotions and experiences, helps to understand their place in society and reduce self-doubt.

Among the many forms and methods aimed at developing skills in working with educators, the following can be distinguished:

1. Seminar - creative lessons aimed at developing creative thinking and creating innovative projects.

2. Modeling games. Business and role-playing games involve modeling a real process, during which optimal professional decisions are made based on the analysis of artificially created pedagogical situations.

3. Collective problem solving, group discussion or brainstorming; training in small groups to improve professional skills; scientific and practical conferences dedicated to methods of self-education work, the results of innovative activities of a preschool educational institution.

4. Pedagogical circle - directs educators to the study of the latest research in the field of psychology and pedagogy, methodological literature, helps to identify various approaches to solving pedagogical problems, improves the skills of logical thinking and substantiation of one's position, teaches conciseness, accuracy, correctness of statements. This form provides criteria for evaluating the answers, speeches and actions of participants:

- general knowledge;
- professional knowledge, abilities, skills;
- ability to get out of a difficult situation, speed.

5. The business game can be used not only as a test lesson based on the results of a theoretical seminar on a problem relevant for a preschool educational institution, but also in developing new solutions to the problem. For example: “Is it easy to be a preschooler?”

6. Idea bank - a rational way to collectively solve problems that cannot be solved using traditional methods at this stage. For example: “Game Ecology”, “Fair of Pedagogical Ideas”, “The Best Developing Game”[1].

7. Master Class. Its main purpose is to get acquainted with pedagogical experience, work system, author's findings and everything that helps the educator achieve the best results.

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